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MOTIVATIONAL DYNAMICS OF THE CREATIVE GESTURE IN BUTŌ DANCE

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Editorial Note

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Antonio Leto

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Introduzione

This thesis addresses the study of the relationship between motivation and creativity in choreutic and performative contexts, with a focus on butō dance, a form of contemporary Japanese dance that has now spread worldwide.

Butō was born in the second half of the 20th century from the ashes of a Japan militarily defeated and subjected to a collective cultural trauma (Alexander, 2004; Hashimoto, 2015; Nagata et al., 2015), a trauma that had already been triggered before the war by the collapse of the values cultivated and preserved during the long isolation of the Edo period (Koh & Takeshima, 2020). Within this context of awakening from a collective traumatic experience (Orlando, 2001), between the late 1950s and early 1960s a group of Japanese artists with complex personalities emerged, later becoming global icons of creative and divergent thought. Among these, the best known also in the West are Yukio Mishima, the “cursed” writer nostalgic for the values of traditional Japan of the Meiji era, and Yoko Ono—filmmaker, musician, but above all Fluxus artist, among the first to explore conceptual art and performance art.

The butō of its founders Tatsumi Hijikata and Kazuo Ōno developed within this cultural movement, characterized by a dynamic conflict between conservative drives—reacting to the cultural influence of the countries that had won the war—and innovative drives that opposed some of those influences, seeking to deconstruct them to create new artistic perspectives (Sanders, 1988, pp. 149–150).

The choice of this topic also stems from the curiosity to investigate what remains today of the founding motivations in those who continue to practice this form of dance-theatre in Japan and across the world.

The parody of gender roles and the homoeroticism staged by Hijikata in Japan in 1959 undoubtedly carried a strong macro-motivation with a social and political purpose (Curtin, 2011). According to Fraleigh (2024), one may speak of Hijikata’s “politically motivated butō.”

More specifically, however, it is also necessary to consider operational aspects and choreographic techniques—devices that move dancers’ bodies. Nudity and white-painted bodies alternate with wide costumes and heavy make-up. In contrast to classical Japanese theatre, masks are not used: the painted face sometimes remains expressionless, often exaggerated in amplifications influenced by Mary Wigman’s expressionist dance. Unlike German expressionist dance, butō does not seek expression, narration, or description, but rather impression and evocation.

Communication with the spectator takes place only if the dancer’s impulse comes from within—from a memory, an emotion, an image—something lived and embodied, not merely narrated or represented. Gender inversion, with the consequent use of feminine costumes by Hijikata and Ōno, responds to dramaturgical functions very different from those in drag queen or cross-dressing performances (Schwartz, 2019).

By staging *Forbidden Colors* (Kinjiki), a butō performance loosely inspired by Mishima’s novel of the same name, Hijikata most likely knew he would be censored and expelled from the Tokyo Modern Dance Association.

What remains today of the initial drives of this revolutionary dance? The hypothesis is that what happened to Martha Graham may also apply to butō: Graham, once a revolutionary innovator of choreographic praxis, became fixed in history as the founder of American modern dance, her creative processes “frozen” in a frame that erased her original motivational impulses—leaving only simulacra of her initial innovations.

The motivational dynamics of the creative gesture will be analyzed from multiple perspectives, recalling the main theories of motivation, beginning with a scientific literature-based overview of how these theories are applied in analyzing creativity and innovation. A multidimensional approach will be adopted, moving from biological and behavioral aspects—such as operant conditioning in dance practice—to drive theories, considering the drive as an interface between body and psyche, also in creativity, in terms of deprivation, the unconscious, and psychopathology. The vertical development of humanistic models will be considered according to Maslow’s pyramid. Particular emphasis will be placed on social approaches such as Vygotskij’s social constructivism, Bandura’s concept of agency within social-cognitive theory, and Bronfenbrenner’s ecological approach to human development—horizontally and concentrically extended—culminating in the more holistic vision of motivational orientation based on personal dynamics of social expectation, where each individual assigns a different valence (Vroom) or value (Atkinson) to the same objective, pursuing it either through success orientation or failure-avoidance strategies.

The interaction between intrinsic and extrinsic motivation and their synergy in the development of creativity within a multidisciplinary approach has been studied by many authors (Fischer et al., 2019). Mihaly Csikszentmihalyi describes an optimal flow experience in artistic creation, where the body plays a central role. Gardner, in close collaboration with Csikszentmihalyi and Feldmann, conducted studies on intelligence and creativity (Gardner, 1993), addressing epistemological and methodological issues. As the Neo-Kantian philosophers Windelband (1904) and Dilthey (Makkreel, 2021)—later taken up by Allport (1942)—pointed out, the human sciences may be approached idiographically or nomothetically (Gardner, 1994). It is within this dialectic that Gardner’s work arose, analyzing the

creative intelligences of different innovators by integrating Gruber's case-study method and Simonton's historiometric approach (Gardner, 1988) to develop his own analytic method based on four main components of creativity. For Gardner, creativity takes multiple forms—at least five (Sri Kantha, 1999)—and cannot be analyzed as a single construct.

In psychometrics, several methods exist for assessing motivational components; in dance, specific test batteries have also been developed, such as the Dance Motivation Inventory (DMI) (Maraz et al., 2015).

The first chapter will briefly present *butō*, situating it in the historical and social context in which it was born, developed, and spread worldwide, outlining the founders' profiles and describing its operational and creative modalities.

The second chapter will recall theoretical models of motivational dynamics, applying them to the performing arts, defining what is meant by a creative gesture in dance practice, and how this gesture is lived as necessary—and necessarily in ecological (Sarkar Munsī, 2024), social, and political—relation with the world.

The third chapter will analyze the specific motivational aspects of *butō* through a multidimensional approach, examining case studies before addressing its relationship with society, the mass media, and its impact on contemporary culture.

Butō

1.1 Premises

Butō exists in the very moment it animates the dancer's body. More than any other choreutic form, it is ephemeral and intangible. To evoke its deepest essence is practically impossible except through the language of poetry, of art, and of nature, which nourish it.

The first regular performances identifiable with the term butō date back to the late 1950s of the 20th century. Initially described by its founder Tatsumi Hijikata simply as “dance performances,” they were later referred to as ankoku buyō and eventually as ankoku butō. The greatest interpreter of this improvisational and loosely structured form of dance was the Japanese dancer Kazuo Ōno, who became known and appreciated worldwide for his delicate and poetic style and his artistic longevity.

Despite the elusive nature of butō, Tatsumi Hijikata's choreographic method was codified by his student Yukio Waguri with a notation system known as butō-fu. Based on poetic texts and paintings, it was divided into seven “worlds” of choreographic figures, not hierarchically organized but interconnected in a horizontal way that may be described as rhizomatic. Butō has often been associated with the philosophical concept of the rhizome, including by its originators Gilles Deleuze and Félix Guattari. The rhizome, as a non-signifying multiplicity, has a relational ontology based on conjunction and on what lies “in-between”; it is non-substantive, non-hierarchical, and non-arborescent (Deleuze & Guattari, 2017).

1.2 The rhizomatic birth of butō

In 1985, at the experimental anti-psychiatry center of La Borde, founded by Jean Oury in 1953 in opposition to traditional psychiatry, Félix Guattari

promoted a festival dedicated to transversal thought and to Japan, in collaboration with the Centre Pompidou and the Festival d'Automne. Four paradigms of reference were defined for the festival's activities (Tagariello, 2014):

- Humanistic modernity, between tradition and contemporaneity, in terms of a "crossroads" (see the filmmaker Teshigahara Hiroshi);
- The high-tech paradigm, a cross between tradition and a pop perspective, well represented by the pianist and composer Sakamoto;
- The butō paradigm, represented by Min Tanaka, student of the dancer and theorist Hijikata Tatsumi;
- The paradigm of primitivity, of Nakagami Kenji, whose literary works draw from folk festivals and minority traditions.

In 1986, Min Tanaka went to La Borde for a series of performances, some of which were filmed in amateur fashion by Joséphine Guattari and François Pain (Min Tanaka and François Pain – 35th Bienal de São Paulo, 2023; François Pain, 2012).

Min Tanaka's style in those years was already an evolution of butō, whose name is body weather. The dancer's body transforms like the weather. His dance is a continuous transformation, driven by perceptions that arise from past experiences and sensations of the moment. Contact with the earth, very slow or very frenetic movements, contraction of the body in contrast with the fluidity of movement typical of modern dance, and distance from everyday life are distinctive elements.

In 1986, the year of the death of founder Hijikata, many aspects of the original butō appear to have been diluted compared to the initial performances.

The subversive and criminal violence of the performance *Kinjiki*, which took place 27 years earlier on May 24, 1959 at the Daichi Seimei Hall—during the sixth performance of the “New Talents” program of the Japanese Modern Dance Association, and which led to Hijikata’s expulsion from the association—is by now only a memory.

However, *butō* continues to reject the structures and hierarchies of other forms of artistic expression. It exists in the moment in which the dance occurs, just as a rhizome exists when it is in action. It rejects representation.

As a dance of darkness by its very vocation, it deliberately explores the darker aspects of human existence, offering a powerful tool for the analysis of the unconscious.

1.3 Impression and expression

The goal of a *butō* performance is not to represent something or to tell a story. In *butō* dance, the narrative aspect of the performance is not central, and generally the performer is not oriented toward describing anything.

Usually, in a non-*butō* dance performance, one starts from a literary or fantastical theme—or from the emotional experience of the dancers—and defines a sequence of movements based on predetermined positions and movements from tradition, as in academic dance, or arising from improvisations on the theme.

A choreography is thus created, based on an assemblage of gestures and background music. In dance in general, the body is a mere vehicle for the message established in advance (D’Orazi, 2018).

“The starting point for Hijikata was the exposure of a body reduced to natural substance, that has no will to express anything” (D’Orazi, 2018).

The performance may have a theme which, often—especially in the case of a solo—may coincide with a strong intrinsic motivation of the dancer to relive an experience.

Kazuo Ōno dedicated his most famous performance to Antonia Mercè, a flamenco dancer known worldwide by her stage name: La Argentina.

The memory of young Kazuo watching a flamenco performance passes through the distorting lens of an adult in his seventies who, during his performance, reprocesses those perceptions.

The choreographic construction of this performance cannot be separated from the affective dimension, which is its main driving force.

Butō technique allows one to project this memory onto some tangible and intangible physical objects and choreographic actions which, like in a phenomenon of diffraction, decompose the central theme to give it an extension in space and time—but above all, to allow some unconscious and uncontrollable aspects to emerge.

These aspects, also due to their archetypal nature, will resonate with the unconscious of the spectator.

Thus, the aim is to live or relive an experience, to activate specific mental states, or even to make use of the experience associated with certain neuromotor automatisms that humans share with other species, in order to evoke the traces that these automatisms necessarily leave in the unconscious.

The relationship between expression and impression has been analyzed starting from the study of the emotional residue of a neutral face. A neutral face tends to carry expressive traces of the previous emotional state (Albohn & Adams, 2021).

1.4 The dead body, the empty body, the body without organs

1.4.1 Definitions

In order to activate this device for the transmission of emotions, the body must start from a state of neutrality.

According to (Ekman & Friesen, 1978, p. 73), neutral is the basic expression for actors. Ekman also theorized the existence of microexpressions capable of revealing truths that one tries to conceal on a voluntary level.

For other authors, neutrality is a meeting point between the vertical activation state (arousal) and a horizontal expressive valence, a kind of everyday average expression (Russell, 1980, p. 501); the so-called neutral expressions of actors tend to cluster around this middle point (Carrera-Levillain & Fernández-Dols, 1994).

A neutral expression will always carry an emotional residue that is detectable and influences impression formation. A perfect neutral does not exist (Albohn & Adams, 2021).

A dead body, an empty body, a body without will, or a body not organic to a goal differ from the concept of neutral expression on the motivational and emotional levels.

The neutral expression aims to achieve a face or posture that does not express; the empty or dead body is the result of an inner journey.

1.4.2 Emotional residue

In the case of the empty body and the dead body, the work aims directly at the annulment of emotion and intention, in order to reach neutrality.

But even though the path in *butō* is different, the result will always be an emotional residue that comes from our unconscious.

This residue can be modified through butō technique, and for each dancer this residual expression will be different, and each re-performance will carry a new meaning.

The dancer's body—even in the dance of some great icons of early 20th-century dance, such as Martha Graham, Mary Wigman, Isadora and Raymond Duncan, Lucia Joyce (Shloss, 2005)—is free: it does not dance, but is danced, as if possessed by higher forces. In the creative phase at least, it is not the dancer who moves conceptually and geometrically, but rather something else that moves the dancer, as happened in the dances of the tarantate in southern Italy or in other forms of ritual dance.

Butō, through indirect paths, also draws from the European tradition through the dancer Mary Wigman, student of Rudolf Laban and founder of German expressionist dance, who was the teacher of the Japanese expressionist dancers Baku Ishii and Eguchi Takaya, who in turn were the teachers of Tatsumi Hijikata and Kazuo Ōno.

The CsO, that is, the body without organs of Deleuze and Guattari, is mentioned in the invocation that Guattari dedicates to the butō dancer Min Tanaka and which is quoted in full in *Les Années de L'Hiver* by Guattari:

1984 – Buto

Tanaka Min

Le dauphin des ténèbres

Ses feux Zen sous les pas du miracle japonaise

d'autre circonscriptions du sens

un corps-sans-organe

un deçà des identités industrielles

au-delà des programmations narratives

lenteurs à la vitesse de la lumière

horizontalités animales
pour arracher ses danses au cosmos
diagrammes d'intensités
à l'intersection de toutes les scènes du possible
chorégraphie d'un coup de dé du désir
sur une ligne continue de naissance
devenir irréversible des rythmes et ritournelles d'un événement-haiku
I dance not in the place but I dance the place
Tanaka Min
the body-weather
le roi nu de nos mémoires impossible de l'être
(Guattari, 1985, p. 266)

For the founders of butō, this body without organs—thus not organic to a purpose—is called dead body.

Kazuo Ōno says:

“If you wish to dance a flower, you can mimic it and it will be any flower, banal and uninteresting; but if you place the beauty of that flower and the emotion it evokes into your dead body, then the flower you create will be true and unique, and the audience will be moved by it” (Dipartimento di Musica e Spettacolo – La Soffitta, 2007).

1.5 Animus and anima

This non-voluntary but active part in the butō dance performance, with which the butō dancer establishes a dialogue, has often been described as Anima, especially by Kazuo Ōno, who—in line with the treatise of Zeami, master of nō theatre who lived between the 12th and 13th centuries—says:

“The soul, which leads from within, must be in a ratio of 10 to 7 with the body that is guided by the soul” (D’Orazi, 2011).

According to Jungian theory developed by Emma Jung(1983) in the book *Animus and Anima*, the Animus is present in the unconscious of the woman, and the Anima is present in the unconscious of the man.

In general, when the Animus emerges into conscious life, it can have devastating effects (Jung, 1983, p. 42), whereas this is not the case for the Anima, which—even when it emerges into the real world—has an inspiring valence for the man (Jung, 1983, pp. 111–113).

It is interesting to analyze the female figures in Kazuo Ōno and Tatsumi Hijikata, founders of *butō* dance, as manifestations of the Jungian archetype Anima which, as the driving force of various performances, also functions as an intrinsic motivation.

According to Emma Jung, the Anima has recurring forms that often appear in myths and legends. Among these figures, the most ancient is the swan woman (Jung, 1983, p. 74), who is distinguished by her ability to foresee the future.

The Anima may remain an unconscious figure or may partially emerge into conscious life. In a man’s unconscious it may take the form of a wise woman, a veiled woman, a princess to be rescued, a passionate lover, a maternal figure, a perfect wife, and is generally a figure connected with nature.

The Anima—like the Animus and the Shadow—is characterized by susceptibility and unpredictability, sensitivity to the slightest offense (Jung, 1983, p. 91).

Emma Jung describes the case of the Scottish writer William Sharp, who lived a particular creative relationship with the Anima. During the writing of

his first novel while he was in Scotland, he began to perceive “that his feminine side was at the origin of the book” (Jung, 1983, pp. 110–112).

The name of this identity was Fiona McLeod, and under this pseudonym Sharp published several stories that had moderate success due to growing interest in Gaelic culture and legends.

Sharp used to maintain a correspondence with Fiona McLeod. According to Emma Jung, in this case the inner Anima had reached an exceptional degree of reality. The integration of the Anima into the man’s conscious personality is part of the individuation process and concerns only the personal aspect of the Anima (Jung, 1983, p. 113).

The way Kazuo Ōno brings to the stage his feminine alter ego La Argentina—a memory of a flamenco dancer—or Divine, the transgender prostitute from *Notre Dame de Fleur* by Jean Genet, or even his mother in *Mother*, where his mother is a red tea table he drags with him as he enters the stage, offers an interesting cue in this regard.

As already mentioned, Ōno—like Hijikata—explicitly refers to the Anima as a motivating function. And the way he transforms into his female characters is very similar to the individuation process described by Emma Jung for William Sharp.

A recurring element in Ōno is the superimposition of a female figure, introjected or projected onto an object or an animal: Divine with the Cathedral of Notre Dame, La Argentina with a young bull entering the stage to the notes of a bandoneon, Ōno’s mother with the red tea table.

Tatsumi Hijikata was the youngest of many siblings, all of whom died in war, and he had a sister to whom he was very attached, who was sold as a prostitute to a brothel when he was still a child.

Hijikata brought various female figures to the stage, both as a dancer and as a choreographer of other dancers, including Kazuo Ōno.

“In 1967 he let his hair grow and began dancing in women’s clothing. It is the moment in which the sister takes possession of Hijikata’s body, initiating an intense dialogue” (D’Orazi, 2011, p. 54).

Hijikata says: “My elder sister lives in my body. If I try to stand up, she crouches down. If I focus on my dance, she eats the darkness of my body” (D’Orazi, 2011, p. 54).

The susceptible and mischievous nature of this personification of the Anima in Hijikata is evident. He elaborates the theme of the bride as “compensation for all those little girls who, like his sister, were sold and could not enjoy the simple happiness of marriage” (D’Orazi, 2011, p. 54).

Motivation and creativity

2.1 Ontology of the creative gesture

Human behavior is closely connected with movement and with communication through the body.

A postural attitude can be associated with a psychological state; movement, understood as a change in posture, is an act of communication or creation directly linked to a change in psychological state.

It is scientifically demonstrated by various studies that there is a relationship between physical posture and mood states, just as there is a relationship between mood states and cognitive performance. In particular, an upright posture would produce a better mood and greater processing speed compared to a slouched one (Awad et al., 2021).

Any act of communication is a motor act, but what is an act of creation, or a creative gesture?

Maddalena (2014, p. 33) defines gesture as “the instrument through which we ordinarily understand reality in a totally synthetic way.” He thus introduces a pedagogical device that he calls complete gesture, understood as a movement that begins and ends while carrying meaning, allowing one to understand something new (Maddalena, 2014, p. 31).

Maddalena, like (Peirce, 2005, p. 215), considers meaning as a set of possible consequences of experience and, through a phenomenological and semiotic approach, pragmatically defines the kind of function that the complete gesture has in relation to knowledge, connecting this function with the creative gesture (Maddalena, 2015).

A gesture, in order to transmit knowledge, cannot simply be repeated but must be re-performed. In this way, mirror neurons are activated, and thus the transmission of a new experience, an impression.

Through re-performance, meaning is personalized and becomes usable by the receiver as a new point of view on existence.

The gesture of academic dance—especially in classical ballet, structured in positions whose names originated at the court of the Sun King in France—had already lost its semantic charge by the end of the 19th century, having been born in a cultural and social context already more than two centuries old at the time.

Precisely in those years, a revolutionary movement, greatly promoted by Laban as well as by Dalcroze, Dutroux, Wigman, Duncan, and others, began to reinvent the praxis of movement and dance.

Laban (1950) also developed a general notation of movement to show the multiple possibilities of the dancer's body and to allow the transcription of any choreography. For Laban, the relationship between motivation and gesture understood as movement is fundamental. His choreological notation is capable of transcribing even emotional and motivational aspects.

An evolution of this method of analysis and notation of movement is the Laban/Bartenieff system.

2.2 Motivation in the creative field

2.2.1 Operant conditioning and dance

In the teaching and practice of academic choreutic arts—but not only in this field—it can be said that the more or less conscious reinforcement of reflex arcs is at the base of a didactic system that leads to the learning of an art during the early phases of development.

It is scientifically proven that operant conditioning interacts with the neural plasticity of the central nervous system even at the level of the spinal cord.

In athletes who practice running, the Hoffmann reflex (H-reflex) of the gastrocnemius, which is strongly involved in locomotion and particularly in running, is much faster than in untrained individuals. Likewise, in dancers, the Hoffmann reflex of the soleus, which is activated in maintaining upright posture and en pointe positions, is much faster than in untrained subjects (Thompson & Wolpaw, 2014).

For behaviorists like Skinner, teaching/learning is based on the reinforcement of reflexes through feedback from interaction with the environment.

This type of learning, alongside the learning of written language, occurs more effectively if teaching begins during what Piaget defined as the preoperational period, around 5–6 years of age.

But the motivation to follow music by dancing seems to have even earlier origins. According to a recent study (Kim & Schachner, 2023), 90% of children produce a recognizable dance by 12.8 months of age, in many cases even daily.

In 80% of cases, imitation of danced gestures appears by 17.9 months of age.

This study shows that tendencies and motivation to follow music appear early, and that the processes of learning and development produce qualitative variations in dance during the first two years of life (Kim & Schachner, 2023).

Early learning of reflex arcs in classical and academic dance is very important. In the case of butō, the aim is not to limit movement to the classical

canons of dance, but to stimulate other innate reflexes and to evoke their unconscious trace.

2.2.2 Social constructivism and the role of language

Vygotskij (2022, pp. 107–114) places himself within the dialectic between what he calls reflexology—which later developed into Skinner’s operant conditioning—and Piaget’s theory of developmental stages, during which the mechanisms of accommodation and assimilation operate.

As in the sliding of two very close planes, the two theories produce a misalignment that, for Vygotskij (2022, pp. 107–114), gives rise to a third theory in which developmental stages are not necessarily universal, but, in a manner more similar to Erik Erikson’s theory, are activated and deactivated following the emergence or resolution of a problem—and moreover, vary according to culture.

Development is influenced by teaching/learning, and vice versa, in a bidirectional process.

Language is the tool of knowledge that allows the child to form thought, and since language is closely linked to the culture of origin, development depends on the culture and society of origin and cannot be entirely universal.

The third plane produced by Vygotsky’s theory is characterized by a new concept that is also very important in the study of motivation: the zone of proximal development, characterized by the distance between what the individual can do alone and what they can do with the support of an adult or a more competent peer.

The perception of this distance generates a driving force that enables the state change.

In this sense, the distinction Vygotsky makes regarding the motivation to learn spoken language and written language is particularly interesting.

In the first case, motivation is linked to a survival drive tied to biological needs, since the child begins to use the first forms of spoken language to express hunger, thirst, or pain.

In the case of written language, motivation is more related to the need for social interaction (Vygotskij, 2022, pp. 107–114).

The first period of dance study usually coincides with the learning of written language.

One of the exercises devised by Kazuo Ōno during the creation of his masterpiece *La Argentina* consists in tracing large imaginary lines in space with the index finger, then beginning to write one's name in the air, letting the body follow the movement of the hand while dancing.

2.2.3 The bioecological approach

Along the lines of Vygotsky's sociocultural theory, Bronfenbrenner segments the environment into five levels that, in the most recent formulations of the theory, change over time, in an approach he defines as bioecological. The individual is placed at the center of concentric rings. Each of these represents a level of social interaction. This highly valuable theory, born and refined in the 1970s and widely used since the 1980s, has undergone several revisions. Recently, it has been emphasized that culture is not separate from the individual but resides in our cognitive and motivational processes, whereas Bronfenbrenner relegated it to the macrosystem in his model. For this reason, Vygotsky's sociocultural theory and the work of his followers Rogoff and Weisner are reintegrated into Bronfenbrenner's bioecological theory to create a new model of a cultural microsystem structured as a spiral and governed by the chronos dimension, which, by making the temporal dimension explicit, accounts for historical and social changes (Vélez-Agosto et al., 2017).

2.2.4 Drives, needs, and movement. The dopaminergic system

From a biological perspective based on the concept of homeostasis, need is generated by a physiological alteration of an organism's equilibrium. If the need is met, the original balance is restored. The body without organs described by Deleuze is not oriented toward a purpose, similarly to the dead body of Hijikata and Ōno. The transcendence of basic drives in favor of a higher, metaphysical motivation is a possible interpretation of the *butō* poetics. However, movement is a primary need of the individual, and motivation, understood as a force that tends to restore equilibrium, shares an important structure: the dopaminergic system. Dopaminergic neurons in the midbrain modulate the motivation for action—and thus for movement—based on distinct signals related to aversive or rewarding stimuli (Bromberg-Martin et al., 2010). Dopaminergic neurons do not transmit individual motivational signals but rather a combination of them. Some dopaminergic neurons are engaged in assigning motivational values, promoting actions that obtain a reward and avoiding aversive events in a sort of motivational weaving that considers multiple signals. Others provide fast and direct responses to potentially more important events (Bromberg-Martin et al., 2010). A meta-analysis considering 15 studies selected from a total of 940 in the PUBMED database examined the bidirectional relationship between physical activity and dopaminergic activation (Marques et al., 2021). On the one hand, it was inferred that increased dopamine release does not have short-term effects on the quality of physical activity; however, it was hypothesized that a tendency for greater dopamine release, even due to specific genetic traits, may be associated with higher levels of habitual physical activity (Marques et al., 2021). On the other hand, it has been widely demonstrated that regular physical activity produces greater dopamine release and benefits

for both mental and physical health (Marques et al., 2021). Parkinson's disease is a multifactorial neurodegenerative neuromotor disorder involving the dopaminergic neurons of the locus coeruleus and the substantia nigra. Various studies attest to a positive effect of choreutic practice on mood, regardless of the style (Rametta, 2018). Some styles may be more effective, such as popping—where one trembles to the beat of the music (Rametta, 2018)—or even butō for its unconventional approach to rhythm and movement.

2.2.5 The humanistic approach and Maslow's pyramid

Maslow's pyramid describes the hierarchy of human needs: a higher-level need cannot be satisfied unless lower-level needs have been fulfilled. Among the basic needs is movement. This model is very useful, for example, in the educational field for determining motivational strategies to foster student learning. However, it is important to highlight several criticisms that have been raised against the model of the hierarchy of needs. The low scientific validity of this model probably stems from the choice of a non-representative sample, consisting of top individuals within a college population and of great academics such as Einstein. The model produced by Maslow is strongly ethnocentric, failing to account for specific needs during periods of war and recession. Therefore, it may prove imprecise in studies on the emergence of creative movements under such conditions. Additionally, in this model, sex is relegated to the same level as breathing and food, neglecting its emotional and psychological implications (King-Hill, 2015). Finally, some scholars have questioned the foundational principle of the hierarchy of needs, asserting that “it is not necessarily the case that every individual must follow the same hierarchy” (Wahba & Bridwell, 1976). Thus, the order expressed

by Maslow's pyramid reveals the Western ethnocentrism inherent in this theory.

2.2.6 The role of agency in the creative Process

The creative gesture as a constructor of signs and meanings is part of a process of cultural and social transformation. As Vygotsky argued, higher mental functions take shape in interpersonal relations (interpsychic) and are then internalized (intrapsychic). Language is a social product that transforms people's way of thinking when it is internalized. In this, Vygotsky echoes Spinoza by emphasizing that the human being introduces a disequilibrium between two options by inserting a sign within a situation. Language, which carries signs through the creative gesture, introduces a disturbance that leads to the disruption of equilibrium and thus to change.

According to Bandura's social-cognitive theory, human functioning is explained through a system of triadic reciprocal causation, where cognition, motivation, affect, and environment interact bidirectionally (Bandura, 1989, p. 1175). Human agency, defined as the capacity to act intentionally and self-reflectively, relies on core capabilities such as intentionality, forethought, self-reactiveness, and self-reflectiveness (Bandura, 1989, pp. 1175–1176). Among these, perceived self-efficacy is central, since people's level of motivation depends largely on what they believe about their capabilities (Bandura, 1989, p. 1176).

A study on agency and creativity within groups producing graffiti during the Egyptian Revolution of 2011 reveals that creativity can be better understood as a process of agency in action rather than as a final product.

In the way described by Gillespie et al. (2014), creativity is better conceived not as a static product but as an ongoing, social process oriented toward an open future. As Wagoner articulates: "What we should be focusing

on, from a cultural psychology perspective, is creativity as a complex ongoing process, oriented to an open future, in which social others and cultural tools directly participate in and are constitutive of.” (Wagoner, 2015, p. 125)

In the case of graffiti production during the Egyptian Revolution, it is not the graffiti itself that carries innovation, but the process of expressing the group’s agency, which, in response to new events, redefines social reality. The essence of graffiti production, like the very nature of the Egyptian Revolution in which no leaders were present, is not tied to a single agentic self but to a group agency that creates spaces of imagination and resistance against those in power. Another important aspect emerging from this case is that innovation does not necessarily have to be institutionalized or accepted by authorities to be considered such (Awad et al., 2021).

2.2.7 Motivation and success

From a more contemporary and holistic perspective, each individual has a motivational orientation in which various goals assume different valences (Vroom) or values (Atkinson). A simple schema developed by Elliot and McGregor (2001), drawing on the theories of McClelland and Atkinson, known as AGT (Achievement Goal Theory), relates success and failure orientation to mastery and performance goals.

2.2.8 The optimal experience of flow

In the 1970s, Csíkszentmihályi and Getzels studied the activity of artists engaged in the production of artworks, noting that when the artist is satisfied with the progress of their creation, they become completely absorbed in the work, even forgetting to satisfy some primary needs (Csíkszentmihályi, 1990). The creative process and intrinsic motivation feed each other.

Csikszentmihályi also identified a personality type particularly predisposed to this kind of experience. Those with an autotelic personality are able to enjoy their activity in most situations. This personality type may also be associated with non-egocentric individualism. Being focused on pursuing one's goals as such, and therefore for an intrinsic motivation, does not exclude a concern for others' well-being; one might even cite the case of purpose-oriented leadership, in which the leader's goals become the group's goals. In the preliminary considerations of an extensive study on creativity, (Csikszentmihályi, 1997) defines two important concepts for analyzing creativity:

The domain: understood as the area of knowledge in which the creative person operates.

The field: understood as the creative person's interlocutors. A part of the macrosystem that is accessible and with which dialogue is possible. In the specific case of dance, the subject creates for an audience that will be present in the here and now, but with each performance, the audience will be different. Using Bronfenbrenner's concentric model with its later modifications, it could be said that the creative person's interlocutors are located on many levels distributed across time and space: in some cases, the creative process does not involve only one era; the field also develops in temporal terms. When Kazuo Ōno, already in his seventies, becomes La Argentina, the flamenco dancer who had enchanted him as a child, he produces a work capable of transferring a perception of his childhood self from 1915 into the here and now of his performance, re-performed worldwide. The authenticity of the performance, as a complete and thus creative gesture, has the power to engage in a transformative dialogue not only with the original sociocultural system of Japan but also with the rest of the world, which becomes the true creative field. The domain of reference

for Kazuo Ōno and Tatsumi Hijikata, in Csíkszentmihályi's model, is dance-theater, and their field of action extends not only in space but also in time.

2.3 Creativity e success

In Csíkszentmihályi's works on creativity, from the early studies on flow in artistic creation with Getzels started in 1968 (Getzels & Csíkszentmihályi, 1976) to the large-scale investigations conducted at the University of Chicago between 1990 and 1995 (Csíkszentmihályi, 1997, p. 22), in which the research sample was selected based on the significance of awards or "widely recognized" achievements (Csíkszentmihályi, 1997, p. 23), a conceptual overlap between creativity and success is perceived. Many scholars, in fact, focus on studying individuals who have received major social recognition, and who therefore, in addition to being creative, have also been successful. These individuals are easier to reach and interview because they are visible. Among these creatives, many—especially artists—refuse to be analyzed. Creatives who achieved success posthumously are obviously not directly accessible.

For this reason, many studies such as those by (Csíkszentmihályi, 1997) and (Gardner, 1993) are based on biographies of successful creatives.

However, success is a construct that must be studied independently from creativity, and, for example, it has been objectively analyzed through the theory of social networks by Albert-László Barabási in his book *The Formula* (Barabási, 2018).

A recent quantitative study found that among more than 6,300 young dancers from 1,603 affiliated schools, the prestige of the originating institution—defined via its network centrality in the Youth America Grand Prix co-competition network—significantly predicts a dancer's likelihood of

obtaining a position in a ballet company, beyond individual performance (Herrera-Guzmán et al., 2023).

According to (Barabási, 2018) success has a strong structural component. In practice, it results from the structure of the individual's social network and may depend predominantly on contingent factors rather than on the subject's creativity.

Creativity, on the other hand—whether individual or group-based—tends to be more of a psycho-social construct of a processual nature, related to agency, in which success can serve a motivating function as social recognition and achievement of goals, but often it is only a collateral effect.

2.4 Creativity between divergent thinking and deviance

In the essay *La malattia ed il suo doppio*, Basaglia, (1971) cites Artaud's *The Theater and Its Double* (Artaud, 1968): “Never before has there been so much talk of civilization and culture, when it is life itself that escapes us,” to emphasize that illness, like hunger and other unresolved problems of humanity, has its counterpart in its institutionalized organization. The real is transformed into ideological reality. Hunger in the world is addressed by creating its ideological and institutionalized double, the FAO, which manages the problem, making it economically productive, while the starving continue to starve. Similarly, illness is managed by placing the patient within the productive system.

This reasoning by Basaglia can be applied in various fields; thus, even in dance, one can say that from a real primary need, which, as seen, arises already during childhood, dance becomes an ideological reality that must be placed within a productive system.

2.4.1 Creativity and psychopathology: mood disorders

According to Ludwig (1995), different psychopathological patterns tend to be associated with different professions at different stages of individuals' lives, and different professions are associated with varying levels of creativity. Furthermore, creative achievements are statistically correlated with certain types of psychopathologies across all professions.

The difficulty in performing a meta-analysis of studies in this field lies in the heterogeneity of definitions of creativity and psychopathology over the years, but one can cautiously affirm that there is a link between creativity and bipolar disorder and the schizotypal profile (Thys et al., 2014).

In Taylor's meta-analysis, three possible causal relationships between mood disorders and creativity are considered:

- Mood disorders as a cause of creativity
- Creativity as a cause of mood disorders
- An unknown variable as the cause of both

In the first case, creative individuals showed a higher incidence of all mood disorders except dysthymic disorder compared to the control group. In the second case, people with mood disorders, in general, did not show significantly higher levels of creativity than the control group. However, individuals with cyclothymic disorder and bipolar disorder showed greater creativity than the control group. People with dysthymic disorder had lower creativity levels than the control group (Taylor, 2017).

2.4.2 The limits of creativity, crime, and social activism

Like many other phenomena related to human existence, creativity is not inherently a virtuous process. Everything that has been said so far about the process of creation and the creative gesture can take on opposing ethical polarities. Consider, for example, sports or religion. It is often stated that "sports are good," but this claim is valid under certain conditions; it is not

guaranteed that sports practice will produce desirable results or occur in a healthy context. Sport is a neutral activity that can be a vehicle for distortions, crimes, and physical harm caused deliberately by poor practices in both amateur and professional contexts, as evidenced by various news cases. However, if sports activity is practiced with the right motivations and according to good practices, it can lead to improved psychophysical health and success for athletes and practitioners. Modern Olympic sport was born thanks to the pedagogue De Coubertin, who insisted that sports practice should be intrinsically motivated, regardless of victory and compensation. For this reason, athletes participating in the Olympics must not receive compensation.

Similarly, religion in its various forms can lead to personal growth through a connection with the sacred, but, for example, if used as a tool of power, it generates war, death, and destruction.

In the history of artistic performance in the 20th and 21st centuries, there are numerous cases of criminal actions. An important distinction must be made, however, regarding the type of crime, the motivations and psychological profile of the perpetrator, and their social consequences.

Two cases, both arising in the postwar period in countries that had suffered the trauma of defeat—Austria and Japan—are cited here.

In the 1960s, killing animals on stage became somewhat fashionable, a shortcut to provoke and self-provoke shock during performances.

In Europe, the Viennese Actionism of Hermann Nitsch was at the forefront in this field, and the first action in which an animal was killed on stage occurred in 1962. One can glimpse an impulse to repeat the violent actions suffered during the war on a defenseless creature.

Three years earlier in Japan, Tatsumi Hijikata, with Yoshito Ōno killing a chicken on stage, was ahead of his time with a shocking, deplorable, and

criminal action. However, he did not become entangled in a cyclical and serial process, unlike Hermann Nitsch, who, driven mainly by economic motives, continued to produce gruesome actions, even on commission, playing on the publicity generated by arrests and trials, until his death in 2022, each time provoking outraged reactions and leaving us, as a product of his creativity, several expensive canvases smeared with animal blood.

In Hijikata—often compared to the Viennese Actionists—the bloody and criminal act is not so central and remains a fairly isolated case. Probably even in his case there was an initial search for visibility, and many of his performances pursued this goal by other means, but the main instances and motivations of *butō* are different.

Another distinction must be made regarding the motivations of certain illegal and creative actions, such as performative protests of a political nature by the FEMEN group, or collective performances by Fridays for Future led by Greta Thunberg (“We are creative, not destructive.” Fridays For Future takes to the streets in Rome with a collective performance, 2023), and a few years ago the red ink in the Trevi Fountain by Graziano Cecchini, who was a forerunner of the actions of *Ultima Generazione*, a collective that targets artworks with striking actions that do not cause irreversible damage to the works, to raise awareness of environmental issues. Or actor James Cromwell, who became vegan and a spokesperson for PETA during the filming of *Babe, the brave pig*, is often arrested and sued for his participation in animal rights demonstrations.

In these latter cases, the goal is to induce social transformation through creative and illegal actions, so the action, although criminal or illegal, is motivated on ethical, political, and social grounds. It should be noted that in the case of Cecchini or *Ultima Generazione*, the crime of vandalism is often challenged, but in reality, no work has been damaged.

These two different worldviews—namely, the institutionalized and economically motivated sensationalism of Nitsch and the environmental and animal rights activism through artistic activism—clashed in Palermo in 2015. In response to an exhibition of Nitsch sponsored by the Municipality of Palermo, a petition signed by 70,000 people was launched and gained national resonance (Brunetto, 2015), and a network of artists, activists, and politicians formed. Through a dedicated social network named *InContemporanea – Arte Attiva* (Macaluso, 2016), they managed to organize, at zero cost, various exhibitions and performances by artists—including the aforementioned Graziano Cecchini—in abandoned or unconventional spaces. He produced several performances and collaborated in the creation of some graffiti with local crews.

The artists were highly motivated by ethical, ecological, and political themes, as well as by specific problems in the art world, where visibility and funding tend to be granted using subjective criteria and structurally discriminatory systems. Dance, and in particular my *butō* performance titled *Simulacra*, inspired by the writings of Jean Baudrillard and held at Villa Lampedusa in Palermo, was part of this protest context.

2.5 Psychometric evaluation of motivation in dance practice

The field of objective evaluation of motivation is rapidly developing, especially in education and work sectors. Among motivation measures such as the Intrinsic Motivation Inventory (McAuley et al., 1989) and the Self-Motivation Inventory (Dishman & Ickes, 1981), relatively few empirical studies have examined the motivational spectrum in dance. One notable exception is (Maraz et al., 2015), who developed the Dance Motivation

Inventory (DMI): starting from a 51-item pool assembled in multiple stages, they validated a 29-item scale loading on 8 factors.

Initially, two independent experts conducted a systematic literature review and collected a list of statements referring to motivation in dance and sports, identifying 20 of them. Simultaneously, dancers from various backgrounds were asked to list as many reasons and motivations for dancing as possible by completing the phrase: "I dance because..."

A total of 74 reasons were collected from 11 individuals. The two lists of reasons were merged, and duplicates and ambiguous phrases were removed. Discrepancies between the two experts were resolved by a third expert. A list of 51 items of possible reasons for dancing was obtained. For the item evaluation, study participants used a 5-level scale (1 = Strongly disagree; 5 = Strongly agree).

The items were grouped into the following factors:

- Fitness (staying in shape and healthy)
- Mood Enhancement (improving mood)
- Intimacy (seeking a sexual partner, attractiveness of the outfit, physical closeness to another person)
- Socializing (being in company with similar people)
- Trance (experiencing trance, ecstasy, reaching altered states of consciousness)
- Mastery (improving coordination and body control)
- Self-confidence (feeling sexy and self-esteem)
- Escapism (avoiding feelings of emptiness, bad moods, daily problems) (ibid.)

Mood enhancement is the most recurrent motivational factor, and gender differences were identified. Men showed greater motivation for mastery and

socialization and less motivation for fitness maintenance compared to women.

This instrument could be used—with appropriate adjustments—in a large-scale study on butō to obtain a sort of motivational spectrum of butō dance.

Motivational dynamics in butō dance

3.1 The master–disciple relationship in butō

Each dancer's butō is different. The role of butō masters is not to teach steps, techniques, or movements, but to show the path in such a way that students can find their own way of dancing. This role is often defined as that of a facilitator. By its very nature, the teaching of butō tends to be highly inclusive, in the sense that a butō dancer does not necessarily need an academic background or a specific age. This inclusivity translates into particular aspects that characterize the facilitator of a heterogeneous dance group.

In a study on the motivational aspects of the choreographer-facilitator in community dance (Bilitza, 2021), some aspects are identified that can also be related to the teaching of butō, based on my personal experience. Generally, when a butō course is launched, there is a great variability in age, technical level, and life experience among participants.

From Bilitza's study, conducted on 7 experts, the three main motivations of a facilitator of heterogeneous groups are:

- Artistic motivation, for all interviewees
- Motivation for social change, for all interviewees
- Personal or private motivation, for 5 out of 7 interviewees
- In more detail, artistic motivation is characterized by:
- Using participants' physical differences as creative input
- Focusing on transformation, guiding participants to overcome their performative limits

Embracing the energy and enthusiasm typical of the participants' constitution as enrichment, opposing it to the standardized movements of professional dancers

Motivation for social change includes the following categories (with response frequencies in parentheses):

- Creating new ground for change (4/7)
- Changing behaviors (2/7)
- Being inclusive (3/7)
- Doing something meaningful (2/7)
- Getting people to work together (5/7)

The facilitator's personal or private motivation is defined as a general interest in people and an orientation toward fulfillment and accomplishment.

The facilitator's function in *butō* is to guide the dancer in discovering their style without preconceived expectations. In this, there are similarities with certain schools of improvisational jazz, where one starts from the interpretive defect to identify the originality of a style.

In Yukio Waguri's method, there are forms drawn from nature and the animal world, exercises based on poetic and surreal texts, or abstract paintings that generate true perceptual stimulations. Each student will re-experience and re-perform them, generating a new form and style through their creative gesture.

3.2 Butō-fu: Yukio Waguri's butoh notation

3.2.1 The neurological ward world

One of the sections (worlds) of Yukio Waguri's *Butō Kaden* method is called the Neurological Ward World. In the exercises of this section, the

dancer is encouraged to evoke memories of proprioceptive, exteroceptive, and nociceptive reflexes and perceptions, channeling them into the nervous system through imaginative devices such as Michaux's ink bottle..

3.2.2 *La boccetta d'inchiostro di Michaux*

Figure 1 – H. Michaux 1954-55 No Name

The text by Yukio Waguri related to the exercise of Michaux's ink bottle reads: *“You are tracing nerves inside Michaux's ink bottle, like in his painting with ink blots. The first dance is an analysis of grace, like fine jewels or Queen Elizabeth's crown. This dance is also an abstract cry. The ink bottle hits the right forehead. The bottle breaks and ink drips into the inside of your body. Your nerves trace the spilled ink inside your body: from the right temple to the right cheek to the contracted corner of the mouth and the neck. The ink passes through the neck and exits the back. It re-enters from the back and exits the chest, rising again to the neck. The nerves tracing the ink rising from the neck are suddenly compromised. The nerves then become like roots torn from the earth.”* (Waguri Y., from Butō Kaden, <https://www.butoh-kaden.com>)

I hypothesized that “in this exercise, the dancer is induced to retrace the psycho-physical activations of a reflex arc by amplifying, slowing down, and maintaining them for an unnatural duration in order to achieve the state of contemplation of grace and the abstract cry that Master Waguri refers to. At the beginning, thanks to the clapping of hands and the traumatic image, the startle reflex is activated. It is an innate reflex that occurs in the presence of a sudden event, which can be physical—such as a noise, flash, vibration, impact, or pain—but can also be internal, psychic, or emotional” (Leto, 2023, p. 23).

The dancer should not imitate the master's movements. The response to the stimulus may initially be an actual startle response. In the following phase, it becomes a sort of memory of a slow-motion startle (Leto, 2023, p. 23).

The startle response can be used to assess the psycho-emotional development of subjects (Vanman et al., 2013). The first reflex activated in the startle is the blink reflex, which is also the most persistent and occurs after 40 ms (Costa & Bitti, 1998, p. 46). The other components follow in order with the following average latencies (Woodworth & Schlosberg, 1956): mouth opening (69 ms), forward head movement (83 ms), neck muscle activation (88 ms). The response wave then follows through the shoulders, abdomen, and finally reaches the knees with a latency of about 200 ms. The entire skeletal musculature returns to baseline condition after just 0.3 seconds (Woodworth & Schlosberg, 1956).

3.3 Butō and mass media

3.3.1 The case of Sharon Stern and Katsura Kan

In episode no. 12 of the first season of UnXplained on March 21, 2020, titled "Deadly Cult" and broadcast in Italy on Rai 4 in 2021, presenter William Shatner claims that butō is a cult and that Master Katsura Kan

induced his student Sharon Stern to suicide. Butō is presented within a narrative frame describing it as a "cult" leading to the self-destruction of its followers.

This version is practically a press release from the FACT association founded by Sharon Stern's father after her death. In reality, there is no univocal relationship between butō and religion.

Hijikata, the founder, was atheist; Ōno was a Baptist Christian; his son Yoshito was Zen Buddhist, like my teacher Sayoko Onishi and many second-generation butō dancers and Japanese people, including Katsura Kan.

Sharon Stern was a young artist from Miami who became passionate about butō during a master's program at Naropa University—the first Buddhist-inspired university in America—after taking a course with Katsura Kan, a visiting artist at the university (Aviv, 2020). Katsura Kan is one of the leading butō performers, instructors, and choreographers in the world. Sharon became a devoted practitioner of butō and a student and follower of Kan. According to Japanese tradition, the master–disciple relationship is closer and more complex than familial ties (Conner, 2022).

The first teaching she received was that butō begins with the abandonment of the self (*ibid.*). Sharon embarked on a path of transformation and regulation through the suppression of those traits she perceived as Western, aligning herself with Buddhist-based Eastern notions. She withdrew into this process of transformation and depersonalization, leaving her husband, abandoning her Western identity to pursue Japanese ideals. She took part in several of Kan's performances, whom she certainly admired greatly and trusted completely. She began writing in the third person, initiating a process of depersonalization that led to several psychotic episodes, one of which occurred during a performance with Kan's group. According to Kan's

testimony and Sharon's messages, the master had even tried to discourage her self-destructive enthusiasm, but Sharon interpreted this as a failure.

She began taking antipsychotic and antidepressant medication. The suicide occurred in 2012 in Miami, near her father's home (Aviv, 2020).

Sharon's father, an Israeli-born diamond dealer, launched a large media campaign to discredit butō and one of its most prominent masters, leveraging heuristics and stereotypes even within contemporary dance circles and using butō-dedicated social media platforms. This affair also touched me personally, as I have been a promoter of this form of dance for many years. From the extensive press coverage, one can see the defense of Katsura Kan—who is certainly not a cult leader—and the testimonies of Sharon's friends, suggesting that Sharon's preexisting fragility and a totalizing interpretation of certain Buddhist techniques incorporated in Kan's butō, along with a dysfunctional relationship with the master, led to a self-disintegration culminating in suicide.

According to Conner (2022), this story should serve as a warning—not necessarily because of the effects of a dysfunctional mentor–disciple relationship based on power imbalance, which can lead to an outcome similar to that of a fanatical cult, nor because butō practice itself is dangerous, as claimed by Stern's father.

The journey into the unknown that butō entails can be dangerous, but if Sharon's case is an isolated one in the butō dance world, cases of depersonalization, self-disintegration, and depression are quite frequent in Buddhist meditation (Conner, 2022).

The warning should focus particularly on the cultural system of reference of those approaching such meditative paths (Conner, 2022). According to Mauricio Sierra-Siegert, psychiatrist at the Depersonalisation Research Unit of the Institute of Psychiatry at King's College London, one's cultural

background and expectations can predict the level of stress associated with the depersonalization process typical of meditation (Conner, 2022).

3.3.2 The Hypothesis of Emotional Dependency

The Animus, as a figure operating in the unconscious of the woman, when projected onto a real individual, can lead to a dysfunctional relationship. In particular, a form of emotional dependency may have its origins in the relationship with the father. Some hints about Sharon Stern's family background suggest that her artistic and cultural escape also entailed a need to flee paternal and masculine authority in general—indeed, she also leaves her husband. However, this flight initiates a destructive triangle in which Kan quite unconsciously, at least initially, becomes the savior in a triangular relationship: master–slave–savior. The motivation for escaping the family reality, as a form of escapism, is strongly present at the beginning of this story.

Suicide is robustly correlated with emotional dependency (Sekowski et al., 2022). Emotional dependency leads to an alteration of brain function, which in its most advanced outcomes can share similarities with post-traumatic stress disorder and substance dependence (Rametta, 2020, p. 43).

Emotional dependency towards Master Kan, along with the depersonalization process of Buddhist origin and the failed communication based on different semantic systems, may also be the triggering causes of a latent, more severe disorder. For example, we may refer to the case of Lucia Joyce, a promising dancer with Raymond Duncan's company in Paris, and daughter of James Joyce. She had an unrequited love for Samuel Beckett, who was more interested in maintaining proximity to James Joyce than to Lucia, for professional reasons—as he himself admitted.

Lucia was forced by her father to abandon dance, as he believed it to be the cause of some of her behavioral disturbances. She was later diagnosed with schizophrenia and was treated, among others, by Carl Gustav Jung, who stated that he would have been more hopeful had there been a clear trauma as the origin of her illness, but he never managed to identify one (Shloss, 2005). Jung identified a disorder in Lucia's language, but her father defended it as an experimental language of the youth. According to Jung, the first problem to address was the very close relationship between father and daughter (Shloss, 2005).

In this Jungian therapy—where Jung, surrounded by numerous female disciples, defended himself by saying they represented his Anima—Lucia established a relationship with Jung's student Cary Baynes, who interpreted the situation using the archetypes of Animus and Anima (Shloss, 2005). It was also hypothesized that James Joyce was reluctant to see his daughter officially labeled as ill because she embodied his Anima—and such a diagnosis would have implied that he too was unwell. For Lucia, the father was probably a personification of the Animus. As in the case of Stone and Kan, and as stated by Emma Jung, the projection of the Animus onto a real person can generate a symbiotic relationship of dependency that becomes increasingly unsustainable over time (Jung, 1983, p. 43).

Emotional dependency should be studied objectively, isolating—also through neurobiological studies—the variables that can help identify these cases and treat them with targeted interventions (Rametta, 2020, p. 44).

3.3.3 Butō in the Mainstream of Pop Culture

In the music video for Madonna's 1998 song "Nothing Really Matters," figures dressed in white with white-painted faces bring butō into the heart of mainstream pop culture. The video was filmed in Sweden; the butō dancers

from the Swedish SU-EN Butoh Company were choreographed by Swedish choreographer SU-EN, real name Susanna Åkerlund, who studied with Yoko Ashikawa, the first butō dancer, from 1988 to 1994.

By 1999, butō had become definitively deterritorialized and was part—both for better and worse—of mass culture. It had become a tool, a technique, a style. Quentin Tarantino also uses the dancer Maro Akaji in his film *Kill Bill* to express horror and fright at the sight of the boss’s head rolling across the table during a yakuza summit chaired by Oren Ishii.

Many dancers and directors have incorporated typical butō techniques and devices into their works because they are powerful tools that work well to establish an intimate connection with the audience. A resonance occurs between the dancer’s unconscious and that of the spectator through embodiment.

Thus, in the new millennium, butō is increasingly diluted, sweetened, and absorbed by other choreographic and even therapeutic forms. This standardization, to use Basaglia’s expression, leads butō to its double: a butō organized according to principles of social and economic utility, fully functional within the productive context of showbiz and stripped of its transformative charge as a revolutionary creative gesture—through the revolt of the flesh and the heretical body of Hijikata, as described by (D’Orazi, 2011).

3.4 Butō and therapy

For years, butō has been used as dance therapy in Japanese psychiatric hospitals. Its adaptation to psychosomatic practice—also influenced by the disciplines Noguchi Taiso and Takeuchi Lessons—was systematized and developed by Toshiharu Kasai (Kasai, 1999). These systems have functional equivalents in the many body–mind psychosomatic approaches developed in

the West, but they are not directly comparable due to profound differences in cultural foundations, as Kasai himself highlights.

Tatsumi Hijikata described butō as a “human rehabilitation,” a way to “protect oneself and protest against the alienation of contemporary society” (Aviv, 2020; Conner, 2022). It might also appear to be a coping strategy that became art through a process of sublimation—a consequence of the collective and individual traumas Hijikata endured indirectly due to the war and directly due to the poverty of rural life in the frigid Akita region of Hokkaido. The motivational drive toward improving the human condition—a kind of therapeutic effect specific to butō—was present then as it is now.

This motivational drive takes on a spiritual nature in the dance of Kazuo Ōno and is well described by Maro Akaji, director of the Dairakudakan company and one of the most acclaimed butō actors and directors of all time: “to capture spirits and gods in our bodies, that’s what butō is all about” (Conner, 2022).

Many authors note a connection between butō’s spirituality and Japan’s majority religion, Buddhism—even though neither of the two founders was Buddhist. And although Buddhism is widespread among Japanese butō dancers, it is important to note that today, 75 years after butō’s birth, the majority of dancers, teachers, facilitators, and choreographers are not Japanese and do not live in Japan. In every major city—even in Italy and Sicily—there is at least one butō company.

According to Kasai (1999), there are two levels of butō practice: level 2 concerns butō as a performative art for an audience, and level 1 concerns the dancer working alone, unseen by the public. The latter is the kind of butō suited for psychosomatic exploration (Kasai, 1999).

3.5 Il Butō and the sex workers di Cape Town

An interesting case in which butō pursues its original goals in an unstable context—far from Japan—with subjects who face high levels of stress due to social stigma and lack of institutional recognition, is that of the sex workers in Cape Town who encountered butō through choreographer Jacki Job.

Hijikata and Ōno often dealt with themes of prostitution and the rehumanization of socially stigmatized victims through butō. South Africa has one of the most progressive constitutions in the world, especially regarding equality and human rights, yet sex work is still considered a crime in itself.

There are between 130,000 and 180,000 sex workers in South Africa—90% of them women, 10% transgender or male—thus the use of the feminine term “sex workers” (Open debate in South Africa for the rights of sex workers | Il Caffè Geopolitico, 2017).

In such a liberal country, activism for the civil rights of sex workers still receives inadequate institutional recognition. Moreover, “the criminalization—both legal and moral—exacerbates gender inequality with consequences for well-being, as statistics reveal many cases of physical and structural violence”. Forty-seven percent of sex workers have been threatened by police, 12% have been raped by police officers, and 28% have experienced sexual extortion from the police (Matchett & Mbasalaki, 2020).

In this context of dehumanization, a theater group called the Sex Workers Theatre Group was formed in March 2019 as part of a collaborative research project between the African Gender Institute, the Centre of Theatre, Performance and Dance Studies at the University of Cape Town, and the NGO Sex Workers Education and Advocacy Task Force (SWEAT).

The group was selected through auditions based on presence, group work, and commitment. The training included several modules. The first was based on improvisation, image theater, invisible theater, and Boal's forum theatre. The second was based on physical theater, butō, contact improvisation, and body awareness, continuing with mime, storytelling, and Lecoq's physical theater.

The inclusion of butō at the start of the physical theater module—due to a scheduling change—was considered a gamble: butō's experimental nature led some to wrongly believe it would be difficult to teach to a group of non-professionals. The impact of the butō sessions on the group was powerful.

The sessions lasted three hours over four days and were led by Jacki Job, a South African performer who studied butō in Japan for eight years. Each session ended with verbal reflections from each participant, later anonymized with pseudonyms to protect identities.

A strong correlation was observed between butō practice and well-being. Jacki's work—as a contemporary butō choreographer born and raised in apartheid-era South Africa as a colored woman—is oriented toward “cultivating an imagination capable of deconstructing inherited cultural epistemologies” (Matchett & Mbasalaki, 2020).

The participants' reflections show a stronger correlation between butō and well-being than with other disciplines. Even today, butō remains a deeply internal experience that maintains its original impulses. The most emblematic quote, which became the title of the project's final publication, was:

“Butoh gives back the feelings to the people.”

Other testimonies emphasized butō's power of transformation and unconscious exploration:

“It’s very deep and it is helping me get in touch with my inner self. I’m good at hiding what I am feeling, but with this, I went in there and brought something out.” (Alice, personal communication, September 28, 2019)

“I connected to something deep inside me.” (Buhle, personal communication, September 21, 2019)

Another recurring theme was connection with the self:

“Sometimes the world is a harsh place and you put up this tough exterior and then you might just involuntarily act or portray tough. However, ...[butoh] brought me to myself, to the being I am, the gentle creature that I am. It helped me to be gentle with myself, to be soft and kind, to get in touch with myself.” (Milly, personal communication, September 21, 2019)

This last statement highlights the thinking body that, through movement, helps recover the true self “toward which to be kind”—a theme strongly linked to well-being and to a form of embodied social justice that counters the dehumanization suffered by the participants due to social stigma and the long-term effects of colonialism (Matchett & Mbasalaki, 2020).

This study identifies some of the original elements of butō: a population exposed to collective trauma, a social group still stigmatized due to sociopolitical dynamics. The achievement of human rehabilitation through butō contrasts with the dehumanization imposed first by colonialism and apartheid, and later by the lack of institutional recognition.

The forces that butō can activate—spiritual exploration, self-knowledge, inner well-being, healing, social redemption, artistic expression, and political transformation—remain strong. If we understand these forces as motivational drives toward a goal or the satisfaction of a need, we can affirm that they are still distinctive to this creative form.

Furthermore, my daily work as a facilitator of butō dance groups allows me to state that the therapeutic aspect does not lie solely in the simple practice

of an art form—in this case, butō. The therapeutic potential of the creative process fundamentally requires an irreducibly embodied spectatorship (Sabatino et al., 2020, p. 31).

An essential part of butō lies in sharing the work with an audience, however small—in going on stage, and in the perception of self-efficacy through the creative gesture.

Conclusions

The initial motivations behind butō were socio-political in nature, as affirmed by many authors and by the founders themselves. For Hijikata, butō had to bring about a rehabilitation of humanity. In this sense, the original butō can be seen as a search for a complete, synthetic, and creative gesture capable of generating a paradigm shift in the realm of dance—not only within Japanese culture but also globally, with a particular emphasis on Western culture.

Hijikata's work followed two fronts: on one hand, the recovery of aspects typical of Japanese Noh and Kabuki theatre in an innovative and deconstructive approach aimed at resisting Western cultural colonialism; on the other, the appropriation of contemporary Western cultural instances, with a particular fascination for the theatre of Artaud and the literature of Genet. The director of the ballet company of the Tokyo theatre was generally a Westerner. In the first half of the twentieth century, many Japanese dancers and actors had travelled to Europe to study or collaborate with innovators such as Étienne Decroux, Antonin Artaud, and Mary Wigman.

During the 1960s, many photographers and filmmakers went to Japan to document the activities of butō dancers, including them in short films and photographic projects. Hijikata's film work—he never left Japan, unlike Ōno—played a fundamental role in spreading the butō aesthetic and creating bridges and points of contact with Western culture, while also having a transformative effect on butō itself.

From a choreographic practice perspective, Hijikata developed a method which, for some students closely connected to him, led to the inference of an organized structure and a notation system known as butō-fu. This notation lacks geometric schemes, positions, or expressive qualities as found in

Laban's choreological notation, and instead uses suggestions, paintings, and external images that can induce psychological states or directly provoke particularly unusual postures capable of eliciting reflexive reactions and subtle emotional residues. These are layered over the actorly neutrality of the nearly still, dead body, contrasting with other moments of frantic movements and exaggerated facial expressions.

Having worked with various Japanese masters, including Yoshito Ōno during a workshop in Palermo in 2005, I quickly learned that students are continually discouraged from imitating the master. Typically, a prompt such as those described above is given for an improvisation that each student must develop individually, having internalized the guidance. Each student is pushed toward creating their own *butō*.

The initial prompt is usually very strong and, in many cases, capable of generating a shock. Just as *butō* as a dance style was born out of a cultural trauma that provided the initial energy for a macrosystemic creative gesture with global resonance, in the more microsystemic context of the dance studio, beginners are often motivated by a powerful image. The dancer's neuromuscular system responds personally, re-performing, re-tracing a pain or an ecstasy rather than repeating geometric or emotional externalizations.

In this sense, the image, the memory, the posture, and the loss of gravitational and emotional balance become motivators for the dancer's action—the engine that moves them from point A to point B in a complete and personal creative gesture. The choreographer may then assemble the sequences of these gestures, each personalized by the dancer, from which a universal, and therefore archetypal, construct emerges that communicates directly with the viewer's unconscious.

The dancers of the Sankai Juku group offer an excellent example of what a collective butō choreography can be. Figure 2 – Sankai Juku (source: Wikimedia).

Figura 2 – Sankai Juku (fonte wikimedia)

Among the performative suggestions, the most difficult to dance are also the most poetic and delicate—those where there is no strong shock or extreme posture, but rather the pursuit of a subtle sensation or elusive image, a metaphysical concept that becomes flesh (embodiment).

Through embodiment, it becomes possible to act on the viewer's unconscious, producing impressions and resonances in what Kasai (1999) refers to as level 2 of butō.

The analysis of a news case in which the suicide of a butō dancer provides a point of reflection on the motivational dynamics of those approaching an art form like butō—one which, despite its deterritorialization and global spread, originates in a different cultural system—also highlights the dangers of pursuing a process of self-neutralization on stage that can, in extreme cases, become a real-life process of depersonalization and self-destruction, with catastrophic consequences.

In the case of the Sex Workers Theatre Group, it was shown that a good practice of butō with individuals subjected to social stigma and violence in dysfunctional contexts of social and institutional conflict produces positive effects: improved mood, self-perception, self-awareness, and recovery of identity and humanity, thanks to an inner exploration in a protected environment.

With reference to this latter study, it can be affirmed that butō—despite now being more widespread outside Japan and having undergone various influences and transformations—has, in many cases, managed to retain its original motivational drives: artistic, socio-political, and rehabilitative in nature.

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